

Creep Resistance and Microstructure Evolution in P23/P91 Welds

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Abstract.

The paper summarizes the results of investigations on heterogeneous P23/P91 welds after long-term creep exposure at temperatures of 500, 550 and 600 °C. Two variants of welds were studied: In Weld A, the filler material corresponded to P91 steel, while in Weld B the chemical composition of the consumable weld matched P23 steel. The creep rupture strength values of Weld A exceeded those of Weld B at all testing temperatures. Most failures in the cross-weld specimens occurred in the partially decarburized zones of P23 or WM23 steel. Creep ductility was less than 9 %. Results of investigations on minor phases were in good agreement with kinetic simulations that considered a 0.1 mm fusion zone. Microstructural studies proved that carburization occurred in the P23/P91 weld fusion zones. Partial decarburization of P23 steel/WM23 was accompanied by dissolution of M_7C_3 and $M_{23}C_6$ particles, and detailed studies revealed precipitation of the $Fe_2(W,Mo)$ Laves phase in decarburized areas. Thermodynamic simulations proved that the appearance of this phase in partially decarburized P23 steel or WM23 is related to a reduction in the carbon content in these areas. According to the results of the creep test, the EBSD investigations revealed a better microstructural stability of the partially decarburized P23 steel in Weld A.

Keywords: Heterogeneous welds P23/P91, creep behavior, fusion zone, microstructural evolution, thermodynamic simulation, kinetic simulation, minor phases.

1. Introduction

Heterogeneous welds of bainitic 2.5CrMo(W)V and martensitic (9-12) %Cr steels are frequently used in modern thermal power plants to compensate for local differences in temperature, pressure, and corrosive/oxidation environment [1-5]. The microstructural stability of these joints during thermal exposure or creep can be significantly affected by redistribution of interstitial elements across the fusion boundary. It is driven by gradients of the activities of these elements, especially of carbon [6]. Interstitial atoms move to areas with a lower activity, and the diffusion flux is approximately proportional to the absolute value of the activity difference. Gradual decarburization can cause weakening of the low-alloy steel zone adjacent to the high-alloy steel fusion zone. The microstructure gradients in the HAZ are related to the corresponding gradients in the creep properties [7]. The creep characteristics of the individual parts of the welds and their mutual interaction determine the response of the welds to deformation. Cross-weld loading is expected to cause complex constraint effects in locations where the creep resistance reaches a minimum and may contribute to local damage. Mismatch in the creep deformation rates exhibited by the base materials, HAZ, and weld metals can lead to the accumulation of strain. The important role in cross-weld loading of the heterogeneous microstructure can play the local formation of triaxial stresses and the processes of grain boundary sliding [8]. Generally, the criterion of the lowest hardness is not valid to identify the location of creep failure in the welds. The accumulation of strain in the narrow zone in the early stages of creep can result in preferential crack nucleation and can accelerate crack growth. Furthermore, residual stresses in welds can accelerate the growth of minor phases and are therefore regarded detrimental to creep resistance [9,10].

Heat resistant steel P/T23 was developed for the manufacture of water walls, reheaters, and superheaters in USC boilers [11]. Modifying the chemical composition of the classical T22 steel grade (2.25Cr-1Mo) by reducing the carbon content and by adding tungsten, vanadium, niobium, boron and nitrogen led to a significant increase in creep resistance [12]. A reduced carbon content in P/T23 steel allowed one to decrease the hardness in HAZ and cold cracking susceptibility. However, welds made of this steel without post weld heat treatment (PWHT) were found to be prone to cracking during the early stages of service operation [13]. Long et al. [14] studied cracking in heterogeneous welds of T23/12Cr1MoV after about 8,000 hours of service and found that cracks occurred in the coarse-grained part of the heat-affected zone (CGHAZ) of T23 steel and exhibited typical features of stress-relief cracking (SRC). The SRC phenomenon can be caused by weakening of grain boundaries due to intensive intragranular precipitation or by impurity segregation [15]. Y. Li and X. Wang [16] studied the evolution of microstructure in simulated CGHAZ in T23 steel during aging at 650 ° C and reported the following precipitation sequence: $M_3C \rightarrow M_3C + M_7C_3 + M_{23}C_6 \rightarrow M_3C + M_7C_3 + M_{23}C_6 + MX \rightarrow M_{23}C_6 + MX + M_6X$. During the long-term creep service, additional precipitation reactions are expected and these processes can significantly affect the creep resistance of T/P23 welds [17-19].

P/T91 steel was developed for applications in USC power plants by a modification of 9Cr-1Mo steel by small additions of vanadium, niobium, and nitrogen, resulting in nearly doubling creep strength [20-22]. This high creep strength is related to the optimized microstructure where the $M_{23}C_6$ phase particles hinder the formation and growth of subgrains in tempered martensite, while fine MX (VN) particles in martensitic laths interact with moving dislocations. These minor phases can form during PWHT or during creep exposure. Furthermore, during creep exposure, the Fe_2Mo Laves phase particles nucleate in the matrix. Particles of this minor phase exhibit low-dimensional stability. The microstructural stability and creep resistance of (9-12) %Cr martensitic steels can be adversely affected by the gradual replacement of fine VN particles by the modified Z phase (Cr(V,Nb)N), which is the thermodynamically stable nitride in these steels [23,24]. The kinetics of this transition is significantly dependent on the chromium content in the steels [25]. In 9 %Cr steels this transition process is expected to be very slow [26].

The aim of this paper is to compare the creep behaviour of two types of heterogeneous P23/P91 welds with different filler materials and to discuss the results of detailed investigations on microstructural evolution in the critical parts of these welds during long-term creep exposure.

2. Materials and Methods

Hot rolled steel pipes of $\phi 219 \times 25$ mm made of steel P91 and P23 were used to prepare circumferential weld joints. The quality heat treatment of P91 steel pipes consisted of normalization at 1050 ° C followed by cooling in air and tempering at 750 ° C for 6 h with subsequent cooling in air. The P23 steel pipes were austenitized at 1050 ° C, quenched in water, and tempered at 760 ° C for 6 h with subsequent cooling in air. Weld A was manufactured using a P91 matching filler metal (Thermanit E CrMo 9 1B), while for Weld B a matching consumable P23 (Thyssen Cr2WV) was used. GTAW (141) technology was applied to produce weld roots followed by multi-pass welds (7 beads) formed by the SMAW (111) process. The PWHT regime of both weldments was 750 ° C/2 h/air. Table 1 shows the chemical composition of the base materials (BM) and the weld metals (WM). Cross-weld creep specimens with a diameter in the range from 5 to 8 mm were cut in half of the pipe wall thickness. Uniaxial creep rupture tests were performed in air at temperatures of 500, 550 and 600 ° C at five stress levels for each temperature.

Table 1 Chemical compositions of the base materials and weld metals, wt. %

Material	C	S	Mn	Si	P	Cu	Ni	Cr	Mo	V	Ti	Nb	W	N	Al
P23	0.08	0.006	0.55	0.27	0.009	0.04	0.08	2.11	0.07	0.23	0.06	0.01	1.70	0.013	0.012
WM23	0.07	0.008	0.44	0.20	-	0.04	0.17	2.47	0.06	0.25	-	0.02	1.62	0.018	-
P91	0.11	0.004	0.51	0.38	0.015	0.17	0.42	8.67	1.00	0.23	0.01	0.07	0.01	0.048	0.012
WM91	0.11	0.008	0.66	0.21	0.009	0.04	0.82	9.50	1.02	0.22	0.01	0.04	0.06	0.028	-

Longitudinal sections through the creep-ruptured specimens were prepared for microstructure characterization and identification of failure locations using light microscopy (LM). Metallographic specimens were etched in a V2A solution (a mixture of 10 ml of HNO₃, 100 ml of HCl and 100 ml of H₂O) and observed in an Olympus GX51 microscope (Olympus Corporation, Tokyo, Japan). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed using a Quanta 450FEG microscope (Thermo Fischer Scientific, Brno, Czech Republic) equipped with electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD, EDAX, USA) and X-ray energy dispersive microanalysis facilities (EDX, EDAX, USA). Specimens for the EBSD analysis were finally polished on colloidal silica. EBSD mapping was performed at an acceleration voltage of 15 kV and a step size of 0.1 μ m. Investigations of minor phases in creep ruptured samples were carried out using a JEOL JEM 2100 transmission electron microscope (TEM) equipped with an energy dispersive (EDX) analyzer (JEOL Ltd., Tokyo, Japan). Both thin foils and carbon-extraction replicas were used. The focused ion beam (FIB, a dual beam FEI NUOVA 600 NANOLAB, Thermo Fischer Scientific, Brno, Czech Republic) technique was used for preparation of thin foils in the WM23/P91 fusion zone. Carbon extraction replicas were prepared in the following areas of the creep ruptured cross-weld samples: base materials P23 and P91, weld metals, partly decarburized and carburized areas of the welds. Identification of minor phases was performed by a combination of selected area electron diffraction (SAED) and EDX analyses. The creep parameters of the samples used for microstructure characterization are summarized in Table 2. Vickers microhardness measurements were carried out on longitudinal sections through the P23/P91 fusion zones using a load of 0.01 kg.

Table 2 Creep parameters of the studied samples

Specimens	Temperature [°C]	Stress [MPa]	Time to rupture [h]	Reduction of area [%]
A1	600	90	5171	8.4
A2	550	115	26,386	8.2
B1	550	100	32,669	8.8

Simulations of thermodynamic equilibrium for P23 and P91 steels were carried out using Thermo-calc software (Thermo-calc software, Stockholm, Sweden) and the TCFE 8 database. Calculations of minor phase profiles across the fusion zone of P23/P91 welds for exposure 600 °C and 30,000 h exposure were performed using Thermo-calc and Dictra software. The width of the fusion zone was determined using EDX quantitative data perpendicular to the fusion boundary of the welds.

3. Results

Creep Properties

The evaluation of the creep properties of heterogeneous P23/P91 welds was carried out using the parametric Larson-Miller equation of the 1st order [27]:

$$P_{LM}=T(C+\log t_r) \quad (1)$$

where T is the testing temperature in Kelvins, C is a constant, and t_r is the time to rupture in hours. The constant C = 25 was used.

The creep rupture strength values in 100,000 h ($R_{u/100,000 h/T}$) were calculated using the Seifert parametric equation in the form [28]:

$$\log R_{uT} = A_0 + A_1 P + A_2 P^2, \quad P = [T \cdot (C + \log t_r) \cdot 10^{-4}] \quad (2)$$

where T is the testing temperature in Kelvins, t_r is the time to rupture in hours, A₁, A₂, A_k and C are material constants.

Figures 1 and 2 summarize the results of the creep rupture tests on cross-weld specimens of Welds A and B in the form of a stress dependence of the Larson-Miller parameter. Experimental results are compared with the standardized mean creep strength curve for P23 steel, which exhibits lower creep resistance from both included steels. The dashed curves represent the allowed 20% deviation from the

mean creep rupture strength. As evident, some experimental results fall below the 20% limit of the creep rupture strength, especially at a temperature of 600 °C and longer times to rupture. Table 3 shows results of calculations of the creep rupture strength of Welds A and B for 100,000 h at temperatures of 500, 550 and 600 °C.

Figure 1 Results of creep rupture tests at 500, 550 and 600 °C and failure locations, open symbols represent interrupted tests, Weld A

Figure 2 Results of the creep rupture tests at 500, 550 and 600 °C and failure locations, Weld B

Table 3 Calculated and standardized creep rupture strength $R_w/100,000_{h/T}$ values for heterogeneous welds P23/P91

T [°C]	Weld A	Weld B	Mean P23 (EN10 216-2 [29])	Low P23 (EN10 216-2 [29])
500	167	137	206	165
550	93	76	145	116
600	38	34	79	63

Figures 1 and 2 also include information on failure locations. In Weld A creep testing, usually failures were reported in the CGHAZ of P23 steel (type III cracking). At high applied stresses, creep fractures occurred in the intercritical or fine-grained part of the HAZ (ICHAZ, FGHAZ) of P23 steel (type IV cracking [7]). Creep damage could develop simultaneously in several parts of the cross-weld specimens, and the final failure occurred in the weakest area. The formation of creep defects was often observed in the HAZ of P91 steel. Creep tests at 600 °C and applied stresses of 100 and 75 MPa resulted in the final failure in the FGHAZ of P91 steel (type IV cracking, Figure 1). In cross-weld specimens of Weld B, failures preferentially occurred in the WM23 close to the fusion zone WM23/P91. Only creep specimens tested at 500 °C and high applied stresses represented the exception. In these specimens, creep fractures occurred in the ICHAZ of P23 steel, Figure 2. In both welds, creep ductility of the cross-weld specimens, which failed in the partly decarburized CGHAZ of P23 steel or in WM23, reached only a few percent (less than 9 %).

Microstructure Characterization of Weld A

Figure 3 shows longitudinal sections through the creep ruptured sample A1. The creep fracture occurred in the partly decarburized CGHAZ of the P23 steel, close to the fusion boundary. Furthermore, fine cavities were observed in the intercritical and/or fine-grained part of the HAZ on the side of the P91 steel, an ellipse in Figure 3 and Figure 4. It shows that in Weld A creep defects can simultaneously form in both HAZ's of cross-weld samples.

Figure 3 Longitudinal section through the creep ruptured sample A1

Figure 4 Cavities in the IC/FG HAZ of P91 steel, sample A1

The microstructure of the P23 base material after creep exposure corresponded to heavily tempered bainite. Figure 5 shows a typical distribution of minor phases in P23 steel in sample A2. The previous austenite grain boundaries and lath boundaries were decorated with M_6X and $M_{23}C_6$ particles. The medium-sized particles were identified as the M_7C_3 phase. Fine particles were formed by the secondary MX phase. The addition of 0.06 wt.% Ti to P23 steel (Table 1) affected the chemical composition, shape, size and stability of MX particles. Cubes of titanium-rich, primary MX particles formed during solidification and did not dissolve even at the highest peak temperatures of welding. They were coarser than secondary vanadium-rich MX particles, which could precipitate during PWHT or creep. Fine secondary MX particles precipitated during creep exposure were significantly enriched with tungsten. SAED analysis of particles containing up to about 50 wt.%W confirmed the FCC unit cell of the MX phase.

Figure 5 Distribution of minor phases in the base material P23, sample A2

Figure 6 documents part of the fraction line in sample A2. It propagates in the partly decarburized GHAZ of P23 steel along the P23/WM91 fusion boundary. The driving force for carbon redistribution during PWHT and subsequent creep exposure is a function of differences in carbon activity across the fusion boundary. At temperatures below A_{c1} , the carbon activity in the P23 steel is significantly higher than that of the P91 steel, Figure 7. Therefore, it is expected that the diffusion of carbon from P23 steel to P91 steel is expected. The differences in nitrogen activity between the two steels are much less significant and therefore only insignificant redistribution of nitrogen is anticipated, Figure 8.

Figure 6 Fracture line in the partially decarburized CGHAZ of P23 steel close to the P23/WM91 fusion boundary, sample A2

Figure 7 Temperature dependence of carbon activity in P23 and P91 steels, Thermo-calc

Figure 8 Temperature dependence of nitrogen activity in P23 and P91 steels, Thermo-calc

Figure 9 shows the results of the kinetic simulation of the minor phase profiles in P23/P91 welds after thermal exposure of 600 °C/30,000 h, considering the fusion zone with a thickness of 0.1 mm. Minor phases M_6X , MX and M_7C_3 are predicted to be thermodynamically stable minor phases in P23 steel. The results show that partial decarburization of CGHAZ in P23 steel is accompanied by pronounced dissolution of M_7C_3 carbides. Partial decarburization is accompanied by only an insignificant decrease in the MX and M_6C fractions in the P23 steel close to the fusion boundary. A significant increase in the $M_{23}C_6$ fraction in the fusion zone suggests that carburization in this transient area with a linear gradient of the chromium content is very intensive. The maximum fraction of the $M_{23}C_6$ phase is predicted near

the end of the fusion zone. On the side of P91 steel, the $M_{23}C_6$ fraction is expected to continuously decrease to a value corresponding to P91 steel. Carburiing of the fusion zone and adjacent P91 steel has a negative effect on the fraction of the Fe_2Mo Laves phase in the microstructure. The fraction of the MX phase does not appear to be affected.

Experimental studies of precipitation in the partially decarburized CGHAZ of the base material P23 in sample A2 revealed that during long-term creep exposure, M_7C_3 and $M_{23}C_6$ completely dissolved, Figure 10. On the other hand, the MX and M_6X particles in this part of the weld joint were preserved. The number density of the titanium-rich MX phase in the CGHAZ of P23 steel was greater than that of the secondary MX particles rich in vanadium. Furthermore, a small number of particles rich in tungsten and iron was present. Electron diffraction analysis identified two minor phases: M_6C and hexagonal Laves phase of Fe_2W type, Figure 10. Planar defects on the basal plane of the Laves phase caused a significant streaking in spot diffraction patterns. The results of the EDX analyses of these two minor phases revealed that the chemical composition of both phases is very similar; Table 4. The particles of these phases could not be reliably discriminated in this way. The typical distribution of these minor phases rich in tungsten in the GCHAZ of the P23 steel of sample A2 is documented in the back-scatter electron (BSE) image in Figure 11.

Figure 9 Kinetic simulation of minor phase profiles across the P23/P91 interface, considering the fusion zone with a thickness of 0.1 mm, Dictra

Figure 10 M_6X and $Fe_2(W,Mo)$ Laves phase particles in the CGHAZ of P23 steel, inserts: $[4\bar{3}1]_{Laves}$ and $[11\bar{1}]_{M_6X}$, sample A2

Figure 11 Distribution of M_6X and $Fe_2(W,Mo)$ Laves phase particles in the CGHAZ of P23 steel, BSE image, sample A2

Table 4 Chemical compositions of the M_6X and $Fe_2(W,Mo)$ Laves phase particles in the partly decarburized CGHAZ of the steel P23, sample A2, wt. %

Phase	V	Cr	Fe	Mo	W
M_6X	1.2 ± 0.6	3.1 ± 0.8	28.4 ± 5.9	6.9 ± 1.2	60.5 ± 5.2
$Fe_2(W,Mo)$	-	2.9 ± 0.5	32.9 ± 3.7	5.7 ± 0.8	58.5 ± 3.4

Note: the results represent arithmetic means and corresponding standard deviations.

The microstructure of the P91 steel after long-term creep exposure consisted of heavily tempered martensite. Figure 12 shows a typical distribution of precipitates in the base material P91 in sample A2. Coarser particles along the prior austenite grain boundaries and lath boundaries were identified as the Fe_2Mo Laves phase and the $M_{23}C_6$ phase. Fine particles of the MX phase occurred in martensitic laths. Primary MX particles were rich in niobium; fine secondary MX particles contained niobium and vanadium. No modified Z phase particles were present in the P91 steel of sample A2.

The most intensive precipitation was observed in the P23/WM91 fusion zone, Figure 13. Particles of different shapes and sizes were present in this area. SAED analysis proved that most particles were $M_{23}C_6$ carbides, see insert in Figure 13. The chromium content in $M_{23}C_6$ particles in the carburized fusion zone varied continuously from the side of P23 steel to WM91, Table 5. This proves that the carbon redistribution mainly occurred in the fusion zone with a continuous chromium gradient. As predicted by thermodynamic simulations, the more chromium in the matrix the less iron in $M_{23}C_6$ particles. A small number density of M_6X phase coexisted in the carburized layer together with $M_{23}C_6$ particles. It can be expected that nitrogen redistribution may have contributed to the stabilization of this phase. No Fe_2Mo Laves phase particles were identified in the carburized area of sample A2.

Table 5 Chemical compositions of $M_{23}C_6$ particles in the carburized zone, sample A2, wt.%

Location	V	Cr	Mn	Fe	Ni	Mo	W
on the side of P23	1.2 ± 0.2	50.6 ± 3.1	2.6 ± 0.3	26.4 ± 3.8	-	8.3 ± 1.1	10.9 ± 2.1
on the side of WM91	0.7 ± 0.1	65.9 ± 1.0	1.7 ± 0.2	15.2 ± 0.3	1.1 ± 0.1	14.7 ± 1.0	0.7 ± 0.1

Note: the results represent arithmetic means and corresponding standard deviations.

Figure 12 Precipitation in the base material P91, sample A2

Figure 13 Heavy precipitation in the carburized fusion zone P23/WM91, insert: ring diffraction pattern of the $M_{23}C_6$ phase, sample A2

Figure 14 shows microhardness HV 0.01 and chromium gradients across the fusion zone P23/WM91 in sample A2. The microhardness increase is closely related to the chromium gradient in the fusion zone.

Figure 14 Microhardness HV 0.01 and chromium gradients across the P23/WM91 fusion zone, sample A2

Microstructure Characterization of Weld B

Figure 15 shows a longitudinal section through sample B1. The creep fracture occurs in the partly decarburized zone of the weld metal WM23 close to the WM23/P91 fusion zone. As evident in Figure 2, this type of creep failure was exclusive to all cross-weld samples tested at 550 and 600 ° C. Similarly like in Weld A, creep damage could simultaneously occur in different parts of specimens [30,31].

Figure 15 Longitudinal section through the ruptured sample B1

Figure 16 documents microhardness and chromium gradients in the carburized WM23/P91 fusion zone in sample B1. The increase in microhardness is closely related to the chromium gradient in the fusion zone. The microhardness level of the WM23 is lower than that of the P23 base material in Weld A. It is a consequence of the differences in chemical compositions, thermo-mechanical history, and microstructure evolution in both specimens.

Figure 16 Microhardness HV 0.01 and chromium gradients across the WM23/P91 interface, sample B1

Microstructural characterization in the WM23/P91 fusion zone was carried out in TEM using thin foils prepared by the FIB technique [32]. Figures 17(a)-(d) show the substructure of sample B1 in the area containing approximately 3.5 wt%Cr, which corresponds to the beginning of the fusion zone. Fine ferritic grains in the matrix proved that bainite recrystallization took place during long-term creep exposure at 550 °C. In the ferritic matrix, there are particles of minor phases. Detailed SAED analysis revealed that most of the particles corresponded to the chromium rich $M_{23}C_6$ phase. The X-ray map of chromium in Figure 17(b) documents the distribution of particles of this minor phase. Furthermore, diffraction analysis revealed that some particles were formed by the molybdenum and tungsten rich M_6X phase. The X-ray maps of tungsten and molybdenum in Figures 17(c) and (d) define the distribution of particles of this phase.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 17 Precipitation in the WM23/P91 fusion zone, mainly $M_{23}C_6$ and some Mo and W rich M_6X particles, (a) bright field, (b)-(d) X ray maps of Cr, Mo and W, sample B1

Figures 18(a)-(c) show the substructure of the thin foil prepared in the partly decarburized zone of P23 steel. The chromium content in the matrix, as determined by the EDX analysis, was about 2.5 wt%. The matrix consists of recrystallized ferritic grains. The circle in Figure 18(a) marks the precipitate that was identified by SAED as the $Fe_2(W,Mo)$ Laves phase, see insert. Figures 18(b) and (c) show molybdenum and tungsten X-ray maps. It is evident that in the field of interest there is only one particle of the $Fe(W,Mo)$ phase. No chromium rich minor phases were observed. The chromium rich carbides in this partially decarburized area are expected to dissolve during long-term creep exposure.

(a)

(b)

Figure 18 Partly decarburized zone of the WM23, (a) bright field (insert: spot diffraction pattern of $\text{Fe}_2(\text{W},\text{Mo})$ Laves phase with zone axis $[\mathbf{11\bar{1}}]_{\text{Laves}}$), (b)-(c) X-ray maps of Mo and W, sample B1

The Thyssen Cr2WV filler consumable did not contain titanium and therefore no titanium-rich MX particles were present in the WM23. The results of the detailed TEM analysis in the WM23/P91 fusion zone and the adjacent partly decarburized WM23 zone in Weld B prove that the microstructural evolution in these regions of interest was similar to that of Weld A. The results of the minor phase identification in the base materials P23 and P91 of the specimens A2 and B1 were also identical.

4. Discussion

The results of the evaluation of minor phases in the partially decarburized CGHAZ of P23 steel or WM23 after long-term creep exposure at 550 °C demonstrate that in both Weld A and Weld B there are particles of the $\text{Fe}_2(\text{W},\text{Mo})$ Laves phase. This minor phase has not been reported in previous publications dealing with precipitation processes in T/P23 steel [17]. Figure 19 shows the effect of carbon in P23 steel on minor phases that are thermodynamically stable. At the normal carbon content in P23 steel (red line), the thermodynamically stable phases predicted in the temperature interval of 500–600 °C include the MX, M_6C and M_7C_3 phases. Partial decarburization of P23 steel is accompanied by destabilization of M_7C_3 carbides, and at carbon contents lower than about 0.04 wt.% the Fe_2W Laves phase is predicted as the thermodynamically stable minor phase. This can be considered as an explanation for the presence of the $\text{Fe}_2(\text{W},\text{Mo})$ Laves phase in the partially decarburized areas of the P23/P91 welds. However, the fraction of this phase in both samples investigated was low, and therefore the expected effect of that phase on the properties of the partially decarburized zone of the P23 steel is insignificant.

Figure 19 Effect of carbon content on the equilibrium minor phases in P23 steel, the red line shows the carbon content in the heat investigated, Thermo-calc

Table 6 shows the results of the minor phase identification in the basic parts of sample A2. Thermo-calc simulations using the TCFE8 database predicted for P23 steel at a temperature of 550 °C the following thermodynamically stable minor phases: M_7C_3 , M_6X and MX . In addition to these minor phases, an experimental study confirmed the presence of the $M_{23}C_6$ phase. Precipitation studies in P23 steel after 500 °C/77,087 h creep exposure did not reveal the presence of this phase [31]. These results suggest that the $M_{23}C_6$ phase can be regarded as a metastable minor phase in P23 steel.

The identified minor phases in the decarburized zone of P23 steel, the P23/WM91 fusion zone, WM91 and P91 steel were identical to the predicted stable minor phases, Figure 9 and Table 6.

Table 6 Results of the minor phase identification in sample A2, Weld A

Area	Minor phases
BM P23	M_7C_3 , $M_{23}C_6$, M_6X , MX
P23 decarb. zone	MX , M_6X , Laves phase $Fe_2(W,Mo)$
P23/WM91 fusion zone	$M_{23}C_6$, MX , M_6X
WM91	$M_{23}C_6$, NbX , secondary MX , Laves phase Fe_2Mo
BM P91	$M_{23}C_6$, NbX , secondary MX , Laves phase Fe_2Mo

The results of the creep rupture tests on welds A and B demonstrate that weld A exhibits a better creep resistance than Weld B at all test temperatures. Long-term creep tests showed that the microstructure that was the weakest in creep was associated with partially decarburized CGHAZ of P23 steel or WM23.

Figures 20(a)-(c) show the results of EBSD investigations on samples of Welds A and B with similar creep exposure parameters. Figure 20(a) shows the inverse pole figure (IPF) orientation map of sample A2 in the fusion zone P23/WM91. In the partially decarburized CGHAZ of the P23 steel bainitic sheafs (platelets of bainitic ferrite) [33] are present up to the fusion boundary. However, differences in the shading of the color inside individual platelets of bainitic ferrite indicate that recovery processes occurred in the matrix during long-term creep exposure at 550 °C. However, no fully recrystallized fine grains of ferrite were observed.

Figure 20(b) shows the IPF orientation map across the WM23/P91 fusion zone in sample B1. Small equiaxed ferritic grains are present in the partly decarburized layer of WM23 close to the WM23/P91 fusion zone. The platelets of bainitic ferrite are no longer evident in the weld metal. Dark globular particles in the weld metal represent oxides formed during welding. The observed recrystallization of bainite in the WM23 contributed to a lower hardness of the WM23 compared to the base material of P23 steel. The demonstrated higher structural stability of the base material P23 compared to WM23 is consistent with a better creep resistance of Weld A.

Figure 20 IPF (normal direction) + image quality maps across the fusion zone P23/WM91 or WM23/P91, (a) sample A2, Weld A, (b) sample B1, Weld B, (c) color coding

5. Conclusions

1. Stress rupture tests of heterogeneous P23/P91 welds at 500, 550 and 600 °C revealed that the creep resistance of Weld A with the filler consumable matching P91 steel surpassed that of Weld B with the weld metal matching P23 steel. The extrapolated values of $R_u/100,000 t/T$ are higher for Weld A at all temperatures studied.
2. The fracture locations were both stress and temperature dependent. The failure locations of most cross-weld samples that ruptured at 550 and 600 °C corresponded to the partially decarburized area of P23 steel or WM23 close to the fusion boundary. This is related to the redistribution of carbon across

the fusion boundary. At temperatures of 500 and 550 °C and high applied stresses, failures occurred in the ICHAZ of P23 steel.

3. The partial decarburization of the CGHAZ in P23 steel (or WM23) was accompanied by the dissolution of M_7C_3 and $M_{23}C_6$ particles. The precipitates present in these areas included the MX, M_6X and $Fe_2(W,Mo)$ Laves phase. Thermodynamic simulations proved that precipitation of the $Fe_2(W, Mo)$ phase in the CGHAZ of P23 steel and in the partially decarburized WM23 is a consequence of partial decarburization in these areas.

4. Thermodynamic and kinetic simulations of carbon redistribution and minor phase evolution in P23/P91 welds across the fusion line predicted that carburization occurs primarily in the fusion zones of dissimilar metals. The experimental findings proved these results. The dominant minor phase in the carburized zones was $M_{23}C_6$ carbide.

5. Weld A was more resistant to recovery/recrystallization processes in the partially decarburized area of the CG HAZ in P23 steel than Weld B in the WM23 close to the WM23/P91 fusion zone.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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